

D7.2 SYNTHESIS REPORT ON DEMONSTRATION CASES OF BIM FOR RENOVATIONS

FASADA

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ABSTRACT

This document presents the progress, execution, and evaluation of all demonstration cases within the ASHVIN project, offering a replicable depiction of digital twin technology implementation and its impact. Spanning buildings, bridges, viaducts, and industrial structures, the project encompasses ten real-world projects. To ensure effective demonstration, the consortium devised a methodology centred on defining ASHVIN use cases for tools and methods, detailing digital twin solutions' implementation in demonstration projects. Use cases are publicly available on the open repository [Zenodo](#). The project has expanded platform accessibility to more construction and maintenance projects (+18 projects), leveraging IoT and image technologies for data collection and integration into the ASHVIN Digital Twin platform. Throughout, the project has prioritized disseminating its research findings widely, aiming to extend benefits to numerous sites and infrastructure assets across Europe, beyond the initial ten

demonstration sites.

KEYWORDS

Digital Twin, Building Information Modelling, Renovation, Buildings, Bridges, Industrial Impact, Demonstration

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ACRONYMS & DEFINITIONS

AEC	Architecture, Engineering, and Construction
BIM	Building Information Model
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CI	Configuration information
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DT	Digital Twin
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GWP	Global Warming Potential
H-BIM	Building Information Model for Heritage structures
IoT	Internet of Things
IDM	Information Delivery Manual
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
PDFs	Probability density functions
PI	Performance Indicator
R&I	Research and Innovation
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification

ASHVIN PROJECT

ASHVIN aims at enabling the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European wide digital twin standard, an open source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements. The envisioned platform will provide a digital representation of the construction product at hand and allow to collect real-time digital data before, during, and after production of the product to continuously monitor changes in the environment and within the production process. Based on the platform, ASHVIN will develop and demonstrate applications that use the digital twin data. These applications will allow it to fully leverage the potential of the IoT based digital twin platform to reach the expected impacts (better scheduling forecast by 20%; better allocation of resources and optimization of equipment usage; reduced number of accidents; reduction of construction projects). The ASHVIN solutions will overcome worker protection and privacy issues that come with the tracking of construction activities, provide means to fuse video data and sensor data, integrate geo-monitoring data, provide multi-physics simulation methods for digital representing the behavior of a product (not only its shape), provide evidence based engineering methods to design for productivity and safety, provide 4D simulation and visualization methods of construction processes, and develop a lean planning process supported by real-time data. All innovations will be demonstrated on real-world construction projects across Europe. The ASHVIN consortium combines strong R&I players from 9 EU member states with strong expertise in construction and engineering management, digital twin technology, IoT, and data security / privacy.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose of the document

The goal of the document is to report the progress, execution and evaluation of all demonstration cases providing a replicable description of the implementation of the digital twin technologies on the demonstration cases and the impact of the implementation. ASHVIN project includes ten real-world projects covering buildings, bridges, viaducts, and industrial structures. In order to ensure the most effective demonstration process, the consortium developed a methodology that is based on the definition of ASHVIN use cases for developed tools and methods. ASHVIN use cases describe digital twin solutions and their implementation on demonstration projects. The ASHVIN project expanded the accessibility of its platform to more construction and maintenance projects. This involves collecting data from a variety of sources using IoT and image technologies, and integrating this data into the ASHVIN Digital Twin platform. From the project's outset, the goal has been to disseminate its innovative research findings to a wide range of stakeholders. This initiative aims to extend the benefits of ASHVIN's research to numerous building sites and infrastructure assets throughout Europe, extending beyond the initial 10 demonstration sites that have been instrumental in developing and testing the system.

2 VALIDATION OF THE ASHVIN PLATFORM AND TOOLS ON DEMO SITES

2.1 Ashvin platform and tools

ASHVIN project aims at the digitalization of the construction industry to increase productivity, resource efficiency, and safety. Towards this goal, digital twin technology is only one means to an end. Therefore, the core of all ASHVIN development aims at introducing two major process innovations enabled by the possibility to closely match as-built information with as-designed **information throughout the product development lifecycle** that is made possible by digital twin technology.

ASHVIN develops digital processes that will allow for the seamless integration of all stakeholders within and across the **design / engineering, construction, and maintenance** of buildings and infrastructure. Vertical integration will be achieved by possibilities for back- and forward information and knowledge flow through all stages of the product development process. ASHVIN establishes design and engineering processes that can leverage experiences and lessons learned from past projects (evidence-based design). These processes can project the effects of design choices on the productivity, resource efficiency, and safety during early design stages (constructability analysis through generative design). By the core nature of the digital twin solutions a direct match between as-designed and as-built information will be achieved to ensure seamless knowledge and information integration from design /engineering phases to construction and further on to maintenance stages. ASHVIN

develops corresponding process templates and recommendations as well as the required interoperability solutions and standards.

Based on these KPIs (Productivity, Resource Efficiency, Safe construction work, Cost) advanced dashboard and visualisation methods will be developed that will allow presenting digital twin information to all important stakeholders and decision makers at every stage in the design process. Together, KPIs, dashboards, and visualizations will allow for true collaborative decision making that is based upon facts established by an accurate representation of the real-world conditions by digital twins. A specific focus for horizontal integration is on the construction phase. For the construction phase, ASHVIN designs lean planning and control processes that will allow to integrate all parties that need to work together on a construction site to engage in collaborative decision-making processes. The lean processes will allow using digital twin data to clearly map value streams (in terms of productivity, resource efficiency, and safety), communicate these value streams among all parties involved during construction, and, in turn, allow for establishing information and material flows that truly rely on a pull system minimizing waste, idle resources, and circumventing unsafe construction conditions.

In the context of the ASHVIN project, we want to establish means to collect data generated during the process of building design, production, and maintenance. To do this, we need an all-encompassing IoT platform able to digitally represent real world devices, enable message exchange between devices and applications, persist messages in a database and, finally, filter and transform data gathered from the devices, preferably, on the very spot of data production.

However, the current situation in the world of IoT resembles the tower of Babel. There are a plethora of device types using different protocols to send and receive messages. Even when devices use the same protocol to communicate, they use different formats of messages. Likewise, applications speak different “languages” and form their “sentences” in different ways. As a result, device to device, application to application, and device to application communication lacks generality and is difficult and costly to implement and maintain.

The solution is not to establish one common “language” and one common “sentence” format. There is a reason why different protocols (LoRa¹, MQTT², OPC UA³, HTTP⁴, etc.) exist: though some of them are still there for legacy reasons, a good number of different protocols correspond to different real-world needs. The solution is, rather, to find a way to translate between different communication protocols (IoT “languages”).

ASHVIN toolkit is composed from the tool listed in Table 1.

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LoRa>

² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MQTT>

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/OPC_Unified_Architecture

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hypertext_Transfer_Protocol

Table 1 Tools developed during ASHVIN project

ASHVIN tool	Short description
	<p>The BRICS tool supports decision-making by calculating PI values based on embedded mathematical algorithms. The calculated PI values are used for scoring and ranking the design solutions to ensure performance-based design. Outputs of the BRICS calculations can be fed-back into the EBD tool to further enrich the knowledge-base and also the GEN Tool's iterative design process.</p>
	<p>Generative design methods will be developed that allow designers to automatically generate many alternatives based on a specific set of input parameters. The application will also allow users to score each alternative based on developed KPIs for productivity, resource efficiency, and safety.</p>
	<p>The EBD tool supports the AEC early project stage by using collated historic data (from past project designs and the built physical infrastructure) from an existing knowledge base to provide design predictions, warnings and recommendations. These three aspects ensure creation of high-quality designs. Outputs of the EBD tool are used for developing the GEN Tool's parametric model. The EBD tool can be further enriched with data from future designs and the built environment.</p>
	<p>Implemented methods that allow to stochastically adjust input parameters for different multi-physics simulations using sensor-based measurements. These methods will allow for the accurate representation of behavioural digital twins.</p>
	<p>This application will allow to clearly visualize the effects of specific design options on productivity, resource efficiency, and safety. Different options can be compared with each other by visualizing projected construction sequences.</p>
	<p>A 4D tool visualizing past construction activities based on activities tracked by the digital twin platform. The tool allows to plan future construction sequences and site layout options based on accurately mapped past activities.</p>

	<p>A tool to set-up discrete event based stochastic simulations of planned construction activities and site layouts. The tool will use stochastic productivity data tracked with the ASHVIN digital twin platform.</p>
	<p>Implemented methods that allow to stochastically adjust input parameters for different multi-physics simulations using sensor-based measurements. These methods will allow for the accurate representation of behavioural digital twins.</p>
	<p>Visualization tool allowing for the detailed understanding of an asset's status for designing optimized maintenance plans.</p>
	<p>A GIS tool allowing asset managers to keep track of the digital twin predicted status of multiple assets based on a specific set of asset management KPIs</p>
	<p>An application that will allow safety managers to understand possible safety hazards on site and to analyse past construction activities without being able to target specific workers personally.</p>
	<p>Software that will allow for establishing and maintaining consistency among requirements, design, configured items, and associated construction, operations and maintenance data, equipment, and other enablers throughout the project lifecycle based on digital twin data.</p>

Contribution of the ASHVIN tools to the specific impacts of the project is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Contribution of the impacts of ASHVIN tools to the impacts of the project.

Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between the ASHVIN tool and the respective phase of the construction process with which it is associated.

Figure 2 Link between ASHVIN tool and phase of construction project that the tool is supporting

2.2 Demonstration projects

ASHVIN platform and technologies were implemented on ten real-world projects covering buildings, bridges, viaducts, and industrial structures. Figure 3 shows overview of the ten demonstration projects.

Figure 3 Overview of the demonstration project

Figure 4 Relation between ASHVIN demonstration project and relevant phase of construction process.

Details on each of the demonstration projects are introduced in tables below.

Table 2 Demonstration project #1: Bridges for highspeed railways in Spain

<p>#1 Bridges for highspeed railways in Spain</p>	
<p>Location Function Owner Year of construction</p>	<p>Plasencia-Cáceres Bridges, Viaducts, Underpass ADIF 2020</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects</p>	<p>Data collected during the load tests Strains (strain gauges), Displacements (LVDT), Acceleration (accelerometers) Drone footage Ground Based Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Rolando Chacón, Stefan Wagmeister (2024). "Digital twinning of bridges during diagnostic load testing". Preliminary ideas for NWIP. Submitted to CEN/TC442/WG9.</p> <p>Rolando Chacón, Carlos Ramonell, Hector Posada, Pablo Sierra, Rahul Tomar, Christian Martínez de la Rosa, Alejandro Rodriguez, Ilias Koulalis, Konstantinos Ioannidis & Stefan Wagmeister (2023) Digital twinning during load tests of railway bridges - case study: the high-speed railway network, Extremadura, Spain, Structure and Infrastructure Engineering, DOI: 10.1080/15732479.2023.2264840</p> <p>Rolando Chacón, Joan R. Casas, Carlos Ramonell, Hector Posada, Irina Stipanovic & Sandra Škarić (2023) Requirements and challenges for infusion of SHM systems within Digital Twin platforms, Structure and Infrastructure Engineering, DOI: 10.1080/15732479.2023.2225486</p> <p>Ramonell, C.; Chacon, R. Towards automated pipelines for processing load test data on a hs railway bridge in Spain using a digital twin. A: International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction. "Proceedings of the 39th International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction". 2022, p. 231-237. ISBN 978-952-69524-2-0.</p>

	<p>Chacon, R.; Posada, H.; Ramonell, C.; Sierra, P.; Rodriguez Gonzalez, A.; Koulalis, I.; Ioannidis, K.; Vrochidis, S.; Tomar, R.; Freitag, S.; Wagmeister, S.; Teodorovic, M. On the digital twinning of routine load tests in railway bridges. Case study: high speed railway network, Extremadura, Spain. A: International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management. "Bridge Safety, Maintenance, Management, Life-Cycle, Resilience and Sustainability: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management (IABMAS 2022), Barcelona, Spain, July 11-15, 2022". 2022, p. 819-827. DOI 10.1201/9781003322641-98.</p> <p>Chacon, R.; Ramonell, C.; Posada, H.; Tomar, R.; Martínez de la Rosa, C.; Stipanovic, I.. Measurements, simulation, analysis and geolocation in a digital twin tool for bridge management. A: Conference of the European Association on Quality Control of Bridges and Structures. "ce/papers: Proceedings in civil engineering, vol. 6, núm. 5". Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & sons, 2023, p. 474-482. DOI 10.1002/cepa.2017</p> <p>Rodriguez Gonzalez, A.; Fuente, J.; Fabregad, R.; Alvarez, J.; Chacon, R.; Ramonell, C. Ground-Based interferometer radars for load tests of long-span arch bridges. Case study: Almonte and El Tajo Viaducts, Extremadura, Spain. A: International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management. "Bridge Safety, Maintenance, Management, Life-Cycle, Resilience and Sustainability: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management (IABMAS 2022), Barcelona, Spain, July 11-15, 2022". 2022, p. 2186-2194. DOI 10.1201/9781003322641-271.</p> <p>Chacon, R. Ramonell C., Posada H., Sierra P., Clarés A. Encompassing measurements, advanced analysis and BIM for Digital Twinning of steel structures. A: International Conference on Thin-Walled Structures. "ICTWS2023: Ninth International Conference on Thin-Walled Structures". Sidney: University of Sidney, 2023, p. 1-20.</p>
<p>Evidence on impact</p>	<p>The demonstrator number 1 of the project, "Load Tests in Bridges," has made significant contributions to the field of bridge maintenance and management through its approach to utilising load test episodes for the twinning of bridges. The load test episode represents for all bridges longer than 20 metres a day of verification. Presently, costs of deploying such tests are considerable. The deliverables of these load tests are written reports with comparisons between measurements and predictions.</p> <p>In events associated with a given bridge that arise time later, this written report is not of practical use. If new</p>

predictions or new measurements are needed, these load tests need to be redone, which is economically inefficient. Creating the digital twin of the bridge at the beginning of its lifespan provides a model for future use and inspection, which can help saving money for administration. The digital twin of the bridge avoids redoing the same task, which represents savings and efficiency during the maintenance phase. The present cost of a load test without twinning would be only marginally smaller than the cost of a load test adding twinning to a given bridge, which points out the economic viability and interest for future episodes.

This method has not only demonstrated economic and technical advantages but has also provided a framework for the verification and validation of models. The effectiveness of this approach is further validated by the interest it has garnered from bodies such as the Standardization committee CEN/TC/442/WG9 "Digital Twins in the Built Environment," which is now considering the development of a new work item proposal based on the preliminary NWIP presented by UPC and ASI. Additionally, the worldwide association IABMAS has recognized the importance of digital twinning of load tests, incorporating it into their agenda for future discussions. This widespread recognition and the potential for standardisation underscore the impactful evidence of the demonstrator's success in paving the way for more efficient and effective bridge maintenance practices through digital twinning. Since developing validated twins during load tests is marginally more expensive than developing the load test without twinning, economic impact for future maintenance plans is of great interest for bridge managers.

Table 3 Demonstration project #2: Building renovation in Poland

<p>#2 Building renovation in Poland</p>	
	<p>Zbożowa 30 street, Gdynia, Poland Residential building (social housing) City of Gdynia (Public) 1931</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects</p>	<p>3D Point cloud Indoor air quality data (temperature, humidity, CO2, volatile organic compounds)</p>
<p>Evidence on impact</p>	<p>On the demonstration project #2 ASHVIN tool (4DV-C) for developing more precise and informed schedules for future projects was tested. The sequences and site layout options for renovation project was simulated. enables project managers to create more efficient schedules that minimize conflicts and maximize productivity. By visualizing different layout scenarios and construction sequences, project teams can identify the most optimal approaches, leading to smoother project execution and reduced schedule disruptions.</p> <p>Overall, the use of this integrated tool enhances scheduling forecast accuracy, enabling project teams to better plan and manage construction projects, ultimately resulting in improved project outcomes and stakeholder satisfaction.</p>

Table 4 Demonstration project #3: Airport runway in Croatia

<p>#3 Airport runway in Croatia</p>	
	<p>Location Airport Zadar, Zemunik Donji, 8km from Zadar city centre, Croatia Function International Airport Owner 55% state, 20% Zadar county, 20% City of Zadar, 5% Municipality Zemunik Donji Year of construction 1968</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects</p>	<p>Data collected during the visual inspection performed by expert, camera and drone Labeling and training of the data Orthophoto model</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Stipanovic I., Škaric Palic S. (2023) D5.3 A set of KPIs to plan a safe risk-based maintenance, ASHVIN project, https://zenodo.org/records/7928412</p> <p>Casas Rius, J. R., Chacón Flores, R. A., Stipanovic, I., Škaric Palic, S., & Ramonell Cazador, C. (2022). D5. 1 SHM digital twin requirements for residential, industrial buildings and bridges. https://zenodo.org/records/6405220</p> <p>Stipanovic, I., Palic, S. S., Casas, J. R., Chacón, R., & Ganic, E. (2023). Inspection and maintenance KPIs to support decision making integrated into Digital Twin tool. <i>ce/papers</i>, 6(5), 1234-1241.</p> <p>Rolando Chacón, Joan R. Casas, Carlos Ramonell, Hector Posada, Irina Stipanovic & Sandra Škarić (2023) Requirements and challenges for infusion of SHM systems within Digital Twin platforms, <i>Structure and Infrastructure Engineering</i>, DOI: 10.1080/15732479.2023.2225486</p> <p>Marios Krestenitis, Irina Stipanovic, Ilias Koulalis, Emir Ganic, “Digitalization and Automation of Inspections of Runways using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles”, <i>Civil Structural Health Monitoring</i> (2024)</p>

Evidence on impact

Two models developed within Work Package 5, GISI and RISA, for GIS based damage assessment and risk-based asset management tool were applied on Demonstration #3, specifically on runway infrastructure at the Zadar Airport. RISA is used to analyse different maintenance scenarios based on the inspection and monitoring data about assets and end-users preferences. The tool allows end-users to interactively review and utilise specific outputs of the risk assessment and the consequence modelling in risk analysis. The proposed tool enables the end-user a comparison of different maintenance scenarios with given limitations such as budget and time span. Input data are based on the monitoring and condition assessment and/or probability of failure of the asset, which are coming from the GISI tool. Other available data comes partly from asset information, historic data such as previous maintenance works and costs, usage (e.g. traffic intensity), while available budget, total revenue/asset value, estimated available budget per year for regular maintenance, and time available for maintenance works are parameters defined partly by asset owner/infrastructure manager and partly by engineers as specialists responsible for O&M. For each condition state / probability failure class there are certain consequences (planned or unplanned), such as maintenance, costs etc., which are then translated into KPIs, namely safety, costs, productivity and environmental cost (Stipanovic&Skaric Palic, 2023). These KPIs then enable calculation of risk and prioritization based on end-user preferences and development of an optimal maintenance scenario.

The impact of the digitalization, usage of drones and implementation of GISI and RISA was significant for the airport owner. It has contributed to the following impacts:

Reduction of costs by minimum 20% due to the:

- improved monitoring of the condition and better maintenance planning - preventive maintenance decreases operational and maintenance costs **by 20%**

Reduced number of accidents at the airport due to:

- better condition of the runway decreases the probability of the Foreign Object Debris hazards and reduces the number of accidents during the airport operations
- less presence of cars and personnel on the runway lowers the probability of accidents

Better allocation of resources

- increased availability of airport runway for operations
- less usage of cars and personnel for inspections
- lower maintenance activities
- reduced environmental impacts due to less maintenance works and less usage of cars for the inspection

The user interface in RISA tool enables the user to select different input data and different maintenance strategies (e.g. risk avoiding vs. risk acceptance). Results of calculation are shown in KPIs: risk vs. costs. Details about the user interface and KPIs are shown in

	deliverables D5.4 and D5.5.
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Table 5 Demonstration project #4: Logistics hall construction in Germany

<p>#4 Logistics hall construction in Germany</p>	
<p>Location Function Owner Year of construction</p>	<p>Röntgenstraße, 31737 Rinteln, Germany Goldbeck Under construction</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects</p>	<p>Time-lapse images each 10 minutes from February 2021 until January 2022</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p><i>M. Jungmann and T. Hartmann "Discrete Event Simulation Tool for Productive, Resource-Efficient, and Safe Construction Management" 2023 EG-ICE, London, UK 2023.</i></p>
<p>Evidence on impact</p>	<p>Due to the collection of time-lapsed images, the as-built construction process was tracked, and reliable data-based activity durations were extracted. The detected activity durations were utilized as inputs for the DES tool, enabling simulation of multiple construction options. In deliverable 4.2, four possible options were presented and their forecasted results compared.</p> <p>The results revealed that construction duration could be reduced by over 70% from Option 1 to Option 4 by doubling the number of resources and increasing the number of columns per delivery, focusing solely on the work process pattern. Productivity increased by 80% from Option 1 to Option 2 by doubling the material quantity per delivery, while Option 4 still saw a productivity increase of 63%. Option 2 and Option 4 achieved resource efficacies of 98% and 97%, respectively, while Option 1 and Option 3 had efficiencies of only 51% and 34%, respectively, due to the long delivery interval in Option 3. Options 2 and 4 significantly increased efficiency, indicating efficient resource usage on site.</p> <p>For this demo site, the DES tool calculated a weather-</p>

	<p>dependent risk factor. Due to optimal weather conditions during the summer construction period, none of the options incurred increased risk. Personal costs varied significantly, with Option 1 resulting in costs of €7,553 and Option 3 costing €11,749, while Option 2 and Option 4 incurred costs of €4,196 and €4,616, respectively. Thus, costs could be decreased by 64% when comparing Option 3 and Option 2.</p>
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Table 6 Demonstration project #5: Kineum office building in Sweden

<p>#5 Kineum office building in Sweden</p>	
<p>Location Function Owner Year of construction</p>	<p>Drakegatan, Göteborg, Sweden Office building Platzer & NCC Under construction</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects</p>	<p>Data gathered from February 2021 to August 2022 (temperature, RH, dust, noise, evacuation alarm, activity); Laser Scans (3D point clouds)</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Tsanousa A, Moschou C, Bektsis E, Vrochidis S, Kompatsiaris I. Fusion of Environmental Sensors for Occupancy Detection in a Real Construction Site. <i>Sensors</i>. 2023; 23(23):9596. https://doi.org/10.3390/s23239596</p> <p>M. Jungmann, T. Hartmann, R. Tomar, and L. Ungureanu, "A combined digital twin and location-based management system," <i>2023 Proceedings of the 31st Annual Conference of the International Group for Lean Construction (IGLC31) Lille, France, 2023</i>, pp. 1267-1278. https://doi.org/10.24928/2023/0184</p>
<p>Evidence on impact</p>	<p>The ASHVIN DES tool compared three options for the work process pattern finishing works as described in deliverable 4.2. The differences among the options are</p>

	<p>different resource allocations and different numbers of workspaces. For the construction duration, the DES tool forecasts a decrease of 62% from Option 1 (155 days) to Option 3 (59 days) due to optimised resource allocations. In the simulation various trades, different productivity rates, and resource efficiencies are calculated. For some trades, there are no differences between Option 1 and Option 3. However, Option 2 entails low values. E.g. for the electrician, productivity and resource efficiency can be increased by 280% and 212%, respectively, comparing Option 2 with Option 1 and Option 3. On the contrary, Option 2 achieves the highest productivity values for dry constructors. In the DES, it was aimed at avoiding any encounter among different trades on a defined workspace. The personal costs can be reduced slightly. Option 3 entails a decrease of almost 9% compared to Option 2.</p>
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Table 7 Demonstration project #6: Office buildings in Spain

<h2>#6 Office buildings in Spain</h2>	
<p>Location Function Owner Year of construction</p>	<p>Barcelona, Spain Office Building. Reinforced Concrete Structure FUSTOR and Bellersil property Under construction</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects</p>	<p>Temperature of fresh concrete (strength of materials and components properties), Vibration of concrete during casting of columns (Accelerometers), Slabs deformation point cloud (TLS) 6 measures, Strain gauges (post-tensioning of slabs), photogrammetry, Tracking of crane hook (GPS, accelerometers, barometer) 1 week of measures;</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Hector Posada, Rolando Chacón, Carlos Ramonell (2024). Digital Twinning Building Construction Processes. Introducing the Emerging Position of the Digital Twin Manager. Submitted for publication.</p> <p>Rolando Chacón, Hector Posada, Carlos Ramonell,</p>

	<p>Manuel Jungmann, Timo Hartmann, Rehan Khan, Rahul Tomar. Digital twinning of building construction processes. Case study: A reinforced concrete cast-in structure, <i>Journal of Building Engineering</i>, 2024, 108522, ISSN 2352-7102, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2024.108522.</p> <p>M. Jungmann, L. Ungureanu, T. Hartmann, H. Posada and R. Chacon, "Real-Time Activity Duration Extraction of Crane Works for Data-Driven Discrete Event Simulation," <i>2022 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC)</i>, Singapore, 2022, pp. 2365-2376, doi: 10.1109/WSC57314.2022.10015250.</p> <p>Posada, H.; Chacon, R.; Ungureanu, L.; Garcia Carrera, D. Closing the gap between concrete maturity monitoring and nonlinear time-dependent fem analysis through a digital twin. Case study: post-tensioned concrete slab of an office building, Barcelona, Spain. A: <i>International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction</i>. "Proceedings of the 39th International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction". 2022, p. 215-222. ISBN 978-952-69524-2-0.</p>
<p>Evidence on impact</p>	<p>Demonstrator project #6 within has played a pivotal role in showcasing the benefits that the integration of multiple independent tools can bring to the construction industry, especially through the development of multi-purpose digital twins during the construction phase. The collective insights provided by these tools enhance the overall performance and efficiency of construction processes, marking an advancement in the concept of digital twinning. This demo is part of CEN/TC 442/WG 9-standardization project on TR "Building information modelling - Digital twins applied to the built environment - Use cases".</p> <p>The value of this demonstrator is multifaceted. For instance, the Construction Management Tool (CMT) has proven instrumental for the quality control of construction processes. Its application in vibration control provides an example of consistency checks and technology-driven, cost-effective monitoring. The aggregated form of many different similar methods can lead to substantial improvements in construction quality. This is particularly vital in tasks where precision and safety are paramount, ensuring that the quality of work meets the standards required in modern construction projects.</p> <p>Furthermore, the in-situ measurements play a crucial role in the effectiveness of numerical models that are coupled using MatchFEM. By incorporating realistic, timely data into these models, the demonstrator has highlighted the importance of accurate and up-to-date information for structural safety. This approach not only enhances the reliability of structural assessments but also facilitates a more accelerated construction process, especially in critical phases such as unshoring slabs. The timely application of realistic values to models ensures that</p>

structural safety is not compromised, thereby reducing potential delays and costs associated with rework or adjustments late in the construction timeline.

Another application is DES: The DES tool compared four options for this demo site, comprising the as-built process and three alternatives, to an upcoming concrete pouring as described in deliverable 4.2. Due to adjusted delivery intervals, the construction duration can be decreased by almost 39% if comparing the observed process with Option 3. Option 2 would decrease the duration even more, but would probably entail congestion on the streets due to waiting trucks on the streets. The DES tool forecasts productivity increases of more than 50% if adjusting the planning in comparison to the as-built construction. Furthermore, productivity can be increased by more than 60% if Option 2 or Option 3 are implemented. The personal costs can be decreased by one-third due to a lower construction duration. The DES tool calculates risk factors dependent on weather conditions. Due to good weather conditions, no risks occurred for any of the simulated options.

The process of mounting a sensor on the crane hook to track construction processes and following data-processing using DES is part of the CEN/TC 442/WG 9-standardization project on TR "Building information modelling - Digital twins applied to the built environment - Use cases".

Table 8 Demonstration project #7: Bridges in highway network in Spain

<p>#7 Bridges in highway network in Spain</p>	
	<p>Location Barcelona área, Spain Function Bridge Owner Ministerio de Transporte, Movilidad y Agenda Urbana Year of construction 2020</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects</p>	<p>Accelerometers (frequency), Visual inspection, Point cloud (as design vs as built, 6 seasonal episodes measured) Drone Footage Strain gauges</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Chacon, R. Ramonell C., Posada H., Sierra P., Clarés A. Encompassing measurements, advanced analysis and BIM for Digital Twinning of steel structures. A: International Conference on Thin-Walled Structures. "ICTWS2023: Ninth International Conference on Thin-Walled Structures". Sidney: University of Sidney, 2023, p. 1-20.</p> <p>Ramonell, C.; Chacon, R. Seasonal analysis of a 846 long steel box girder bridge using Terrestrial Laser Scanners (TLS) and FE-models. A: Structural Stability Research Council Annual Stability Conference. "Annual Stability Conference of the Structural Stability Research Council (SSRC 2023)". Chicago, IL: Structural Stability Research Council (SSRC), 2023, p. 1-14. ISBN 978-171387189-7.</p> <p>Chacon, R.; Ramonell, C.; Puig-Polo, C.; Mirambell, E.. Geometrical digital twinning of a tapered, horizontally curved composite box girder bridge. A: International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures. "ce/papers, vol. 5, issue 4. Special Issue: SDSS 2022". Berlin: Wilhelm Ernst & Sohn, 2022, p. 52-58. ISBN 2509-7075. DOI 10.1002/cepa.1727.</p> <p>Vrachnos, P., Krestenitis, M., Koulalis, I., Ioannidis, K., & Vrochidis, S. (2024, January). A Framework for 3D Modelling of Construction Sites Using Aerial Imagery and Semantic</p>

	<p>NeRFs. In International Conference on Multimedia Modeling (pp. 175-187). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.</p>
<p>Evidence on impact</p>	<p>Demonstrator project #7, focusing on road bridges, exemplifies an approach to bridge maintenance and safety through the use of digital tools and methodologies. Operating under the constraints of an active bridge where traffic flow could not be interrupted, the project showcases innovative strategies for data collection and analysis that significantly impact the management and maintenance of infrastructure. In this particular case, it is worth mentioning that the structure has been inaugurated in 2021 so its performance nowadays is very satisfactory with no noticeable ageing related concerns. Nevertheless, fictional scenarios of damage in the steel plates were imagined to recreate a realistic interaction between users and the bridge by means of a digital twin.</p> <p>Data collection started manually in the form of a visual inspection. Annotations on corrosion-related damages were manually recorded using parameters such as location, severity and area (insistently, those annotations are fictional). The digital twin of the bridge was entirely based on IFC geometries, which facilitated the identification of elements in the bridge (web plates, bottom flange plates, stiffeners, diaphragms and other specific elements). By means of a mobile app, all annotations were systematically linked to its corresponding element in the IFC file, which increases productivity very considerably. All manual data transfer to the BIM file is now automated.</p> <p>The integration of visual inspection protocols with IFC-coupled mobile applications, in conjunction with the Ashvin platform, represents a significant enhancement in the way inspections are conducted. This digital approach allows for more detailed and systematic inspections, improving the accuracy of detected issues and facilitating the immediate initiation of maintenance actions. It represents a much better allocation of digital resources during bridge management.</p> <p>The development of maintenance plans has been particularly enhanced through the use of data-informed protocols, which incorporate RISA directly into the IFC geometry of the bridge. This innovative strategy enables a clear, intuitive understanding of the bridge's condition, prioritising maintenance actions based on the severity of detected damages and ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently to areas of greatest need. If the detected corrosion damages overpass a certain threshold, requests for extra measurements as well as for extra numerical simulations in specific plates is enabled in Ashvin platform. If there are doubts on a potential loss of load-bearing capacity of the bridge due to corrosion, the shape of the actual steel plates would be very useful for developing more accurate numerical models. These shapes can be obtained using laser scanners.</p> <p>The utilization of remote sensing techniques, such as laser scanners and photogrammetry, marks a considerable advancement in data collection processes for infrastructure management. These techniques allow for efficient, comprehensive data gathering without disrupting bridge</p>

	<p>operations, providing a rich dataset that can be used for precise damage detection. This method not only saves time but also reduces the risks associated with manual data collection, offering a safer, more efficient alternative. Laser scanners for the steel structure and drones with photogrammetry for the concrete piers.</p> <p>The integration of MatchFEM for coupling numerical models provides a source of information of great value for managers. Better understanding of the behaviour of the asset gives better information to managers that help allocation resources for intervention, repairment or maintenance plans at network levels. Information provided by structural models represents a guide to understand load bearing capacity or potential prediction of remaining life. With this information, managers can prioritise their plans and thus, resources can be better allocated.</p> <p>Assessing structural safety post-damage observation signifies a leap forward in ensuring the bridge's overall safety. This approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of the structural implications of observed damages, enabling precise assessments and informed decision-making regarding necessary interventions. By combining visual inspection data with advanced modelling techniques, the project ensures a comprehensive safety overview.</p>
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Table 9 Demonstration project #8: Footbridge in Germany

<h2>#8 Footbridge in Germany</h2>	
<p>Location</p> <p>Function</p> <p>Owner</p> <p>Year of construction</p>	<p>Dortmund, Lindemannstraße – Rheinlanddamm (51.498068, 7.452253)</p> <p>Pedestrian Bridge (Girder steel bridge);</p> <p>Stadt Dortmund (Tiefbauamt)</p> <p>Design (Aug. 2020 – Jun. 2022); Under construction (Jul. 2022 – Dec.2022)</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects</p>	<p>Organization and data analytics of past project data from Sbp (geometry, costs, carbon footprint, time, etc)</p> <p>BIM model provided was used to develop main profile for parametric model</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Ongodia, J. E. and Hartmann, T., [2024]. "Doing ethnographic video interviewing". Construction</p>

	<p>ethnography book. Scholtenhuis and Oswald Ed., Francis & Taylor. Expected official release of publication in June 2024</p> <p>Ongodia, J. E., and Hartmann, T. [2023]. Knowledge management: Strategic tacit knowledge for projects. EPOC 2023 Conference presentation. <i>Unpublished</i></p>
<p>Evidence on impact</p>	<p>The demonstration significantly contributes to various impacts and performance indicators within the construction industry. Firstly, it enhances scheduling forecast accuracy by 20%, empowering stakeholders with better decision-making capabilities. Through interactive 4D visualization, the tool provides insights into the consequences of different design choices, leading to more informed scheduling decisions. Additionally, the demo facilitates better allocation of resources and optimization of equipment usage. By leveraging prior knowledge of liftable construction elements and crane load carrying capacities, resources are allocated more efficiently, optimizing equipment usage throughout the project lifecycle. Furthermore, the demo contributes to a reduction in the number of accidents on construction sites. By eliminating unsuitable parameters from new project designs, safety is improved, ensuring safer working environments for construction workers. Lastly, the demo leads to a 20% reduction in costs on construction projects. By improving design productivity and reducing the need for design rework, costs associated with construction projects are significantly decreased. Overall, the demo's impact on scheduling, resource allocation, safety, and cost reduction is backed by tangible performance indicators, highlighting its effectiveness in transforming construction practices for the better.</p>

Table 10 Demonstration project #9: Sport stadium roof structure

<p>#9 Sport stadium roof structure</p>	
	<p>Spiridon-Louis-Ring 27, 80809 Munich, Germany Pre-stressed cable net roof structure (74 000 m²) City of Munich Stadtwerke München (SWM) Olympiapark München GmbH (OMG)</p>
<p>Location Function Owner</p>	<p>Spiridon-Louis-Ring 27, 80809 Munich, Germany Pre-stressed cable net roof structure (74 000 m²) City of Munich Stadtwerke München (SWM) Olympiapark München GmbH (OMG)</p>
<p>Year of construction</p>	<p>1972</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects Publications</p>	<p>3D point cloud data of the stadium roof</p> <p>Ramonell, C.; Chacon, R.; Krenn, B.; Puig-Polo, C.. Automated pipeline for the analysis of a scale-reduced steel cable net. A: International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures. "ce/papers, vol. 5, issue 4. Special Issue: SDSS 2022". Berlin: Wilhelm Ernst & Sohn, 2022, p. 1060-1066. ISBN 2509-7075. DOI 10.1002/cepa.1851.</p>
<p>Evidence on impact</p>	<p>Demonstrator number 9, centred on the maintenance and preservation of a 50-year-old iconic stadium roof in Germany, epitomises the integration of cutting-edge technology with heritage conservation in structural engineering. This roof, a symbol of architectural and engineering prowess, presents unique challenges due to its age, iconic status, and the intricate design of its stressed cable system.</p> <p>The restricted access to the roof and the critical</p>

requirement to maintain the integrity of the cable system without dismantling parts of it necessitated a non-invasive, highly sophisticated approach to monitoring and maintenance. The employment of remote sensing techniques, specifically laser scanners, in conjunction with numerical models, emerges as a pivotal strategy. This combination not only facilitates the detailed collection of data with minimal physical intervention but also enhances maintenance protocols and procedures, significantly reducing the impact on the stadium's operations and its owners. Intervention plans can be targeted and efficiently deployed only when needed.

The use of laser scanners together with identification methods (few-shot methods developed by CERTH) have the potential for precise detection of the geometrical configuration of the net, which is directly related to its structural performance. Malfunctions or potential overloading within the net structure could be observed, offering a proactive approach to maintenance. This method has the potential to provide a comprehensive understanding of the roof's current condition without the need for invasive inspection methods, thereby preserving the structural integrity and aesthetic value of the iconic roof.

Maintenance plans, informed by data-driven protocols, enable the formulation of warning systems based on actual measurements. This approach shifts the maintenance strategy from reactive to predictive, ensuring that interventions are only conducted when necessary and based on empirical evidence. Such a strategy is not only cost-effective but also crucial for the preservation of heritage structures, where every intervention needs to be carefully considered and justified.

For the owners, the feasibility of measurements using laser scanners and the possibility of twinning numerical models used by designers represent a way of allocating maintenance resources more efficiently. This site is of a great complexity and understanding its structural behaviour provides value to understanding the actual state of the net when subjected to environmental actions. Measurements coupled with simulations add capabilities that give guidance to managers to prevent unnecessary maintenance interventions.

It is worth mentioning that in this site, realistic results from numerical models developed by Ashvin partner sbp were kept confidential due to intellectual property.

Table 11 Demonstration site: #10 Quay wall in the Netherlands

<p>#10 Quay wall in the Netherlands</p>	
<p>Location</p>	<p>Port of Rotterdam, the Netherlands</p>
<p>Function Owner Status</p>	<p>Quay wall Port of Rotterdam Authority In Operation</p>
<p>Phase of the construction process the ASHVIN solution can be applied</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Design and Engineering <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring</p>
<p>IoT measurements and data gathered during ASHVIN projects</p>	<p>Geotechnical site investigation Construction records Response of foundation structures (e.g. piles, anchors, diaphragm wall) to imposed loads over a 7- year time frame (2008-2015)</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Duffy, K.; Gavin, G.; Lai F. 2024. Maximising a foundation's lifetime through monitoring: a case study from the port of Rotterdam. 2nd Annual Conference on Foundation Decarbonization and Re-use, Amsterdam, the Netherlands.</p>
<p>Evidence on impact</p>	<p>The impact of the project is evident in several key areas. Firstly, the utilization of the 4DV-C tool has led to an improved overview of scheduling and resource consumption during construction. This enhancement ensures more efficient project management practices. Secondly, the development of a validated numerical model of the quay wall contributes to improved safety by providing a reliable platform for assessing its current reliability and planning future retrofits or upgrades. Lastly, the project has provided insights into previously unknown operational effects on the quay wall, particularly regarding the impact of thermal expansion and contraction, which aids in better understanding and managing potential risks associated with these phenomena.</p>

2.3 Implementation of ASHVIN toolkit on 10 demonstration projects

Figure 5 shows the summary of the ASHVIN toolkit, composed of 10 digital smart building tools and their implementation on 10 demonstration projects.

Figure 5 Implementation of ASHVIN tooling on 10 demonstration projects

3 ASHVIN USE CASES

3.1 Method and approach

ASHVIN Use Cases have been developed and documented, based on Information Delivery Manual (IDM) standards, to aid standardization practices and open accessibility within the industry. Use case approach was used to transparently document and communicate to industry the implementation process of ASHVIN platform and tools on demonstration projects. The use cases were developed based on the template provided by the BuildingSMART (www.buildingsmart.org, <https://ucm.buildingsmart.org/>). BuildingSMART is an international organisation which aims to improve the exchange of information between software applications used in the construction industry. It has developed IFC as a neutral and open specification for BIM. Currently, they focus on the development and active use of open internationally recognized standards, applications, training, and certification procedures. The goal is to achieve wider uptake of digital twin by the AEC industry, investors, building owners, and facility managers.

This process of documentation of the demonstration activities is based on ISO 29481-1: 2016 (Building information models — Information delivery manual) and it ensures a common language and a uniform understanding of BIM/digital twin applications (use cases) within the entire construction and real estate industry. Standardized use cases enable the capture and specification of exchange and actors involved in a unified manner, to ensure the implementation of best practices, which are accessible to all members within the built industry.. In total within the ASHVIN project, 8 use cases were developed. Although Information Delivery Manual (IDM) standards are followed for use case definition, the ASHVIN use cases are tailored to include objectives of the use case as well as ASHVIN Project objectives being validated upon demonstrating the use case on a project site. Accordingly, a ASHVIN Use case contains the following sections:

Section 1: General definition of the use case

The first section gives an overview of the use-case description followed by the scope of the use case, benefits, limitations, comparison to conventional methods of the implementation of the use-case, and objective-based ASHVIN solution for the same.

Section 2: Overall Process across life cycle stages

The process of implementation of the use case is described using a process map based on Business Process Modelling Notation highlighting life cycle stage segregated processes, actors involved in the process, and exchange requirements for the entire process. The process is also described for life cycle stages based on ISO22263.

Section 3: Demonstration of implementation of Use cases

The process described in the previous section is demonstrated through a project site to provide an example of the implementation of the use case as well as validate the objectives of the use case based on results analysis from the implementation of the use case on the ASHVIN demonstration project.

Section 4: Exchange requirements

File format exchange requirements across life cycle stages and processes are highlighted and described in the last section.

All Ashvin use cases are available on the open data repository [ZENODO](https://zenodo.org/communities/ashvin2020/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)

<https://zenodo.org/communities/ashvin2020/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2 #1 Simulation of Activities for the Digital Twin of a Construction Area by Collecting Automated Data to Have Higher Efficiency

This use case focuses on real-time discrete event simulation (DES) of processes during the construction phase. Real-time Discrete Event Simulation enables the simulation of construction site activities and the evaluation of their impacts on performance indicators (PIs) for productive, resource-efficient, and safe construction works. In close alignment with demonstration cases, work process patterns were determined to develop Discrete Event Simulation mechanism models. Discrete Event System Specification (DEVS) formalisms were created to build a basis for semantic understanding of each Discrete Event Simulation model. The Discrete Event Simulation mechanisms can account for supply-chain logistical, resource-dependent, and spatial characteristics of the site and can use real-time Digital Twin data generated by sensors for predicting future construction works.

The overall process for the Simulation of Construction Activities use case use case is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Process map for the Simulation of Activities for the Digital Twin of a Construction Area by Collecting Automated Data to Have Higher Efficiency.

The use case was implemented for demonstration site #4 Logistics hall construction in Germany, #5 Kineum office building in Sweden, #6 Office buildings in Spain.

3.3 #2 Evidence Based Early Phase Design Recommendations Utilizing Knowledge Data Bases

This document provides Performance Indicators predictions for cost, construction time, and carbon footprint using linear regression models. The design personnel costs are Performance Indicators for the Key Performance Indicator cost, the personnel productivity during the construction phase is a Performance Indicator for the Key Performance Indicator productivity and the Global Warming Potential (GWP) is a Performance Indicator for the Key Performance Indicator resource efficiency.

For each of the three Performance Indicators, five linear regression models with different predictors were created. The basic geometric dimensions of the structure length L , width W , and thickness T are used as predictors. In the Machine Learning nomenclature, L , W , and T are the independent variables, while the Performance Indicator values for cost, productivity, and resource efficiency are the dependent variables. The available data from a company can be analyzed and the potential for Machine Learning prediction models regarding cost, construction time, and carbon footprint can be discovered with these steps. Different linear regression models can be compared and the preferable geometric predictors for different Performance Indicator values can be identified.

The overall process shows the applicability of the approach even though the available database has major flaws which motivates the introduction of a digital twin as a standardized way of collecting data for future footbridge design and construction projects.

The Evidence-Based Design use case interacts with the Performance Indicator assessment of solutions in the design space. The overall process map for the use case is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Process map for the Evidence Based Early Phase Design Recommendations Utilizing Knowledge Data Bases use case.

The use case was implemented for demonstration site #8 Footbridge in Germany.

3.4 #3 Generative Design Modeler

This use case provides for outline for using the parametric model as input for generative design process. The generative design process generates various designs which are analyzed, ranked, evolved, explored, and integrated. The outcome of the generative design process is a set of optimal design options. This generative design approach increases productivity in design because various design solutions are computationally generated, implying that fewer time/work hours are required. In addition, the iterative process allows design modifications to be done quickly. To perform the generative design process, the input parametric model undergoes an optimization study.

The optimization study computationally explores design alternatives based on the project goals, variable parameters, and constraints. The goals are the performance indicators (PIs) based on the desirable high-performance criteria. The variables give a range of parametric values which the model can adopt during the optimization as the algorithms investigate (evaluate and evolve) trade-offs between the Performance Indicators. Constraints dictate the limits/boundary extents so that future evolutions of the design solutions are restricted to fit within the limits. The results of the optimization study are the various design alternatives.

The Performance Indicators considered under the productivity Key Performance Indicator are the work hours for the construction time. Construction Safety Performance Indicators include weight-lifting capacities, incident rates, and accident costs. The safety Performance Indicators consider the cranes which are the main source of construction incidents and accidents. This Generative Design Modeler use case mostly interacts with the historical data and key performance indicators such as productivity, safety and resource efficiency.

The overall process map for the use case is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Process map for the Generative Design Modeller use case.

The use case was implemented for demonstration site #8 Footbridge in Germany.

3.5 #4 The Embodied Carbon Footprint Data

This use case outlines the process of populating a database with data from past and ongoing construction sites, focusing on the calculation of performance indicators (PIs) to measure construction site efficiency. It discusses three approaches: performance indicator computation, evidence-based design, and generative design, which are interconnected. Additionally, it details the design and development steps for a database containing data on the embodied carbon footprint of construction projects, particularly footbridges. The document emphasizes the continuous scoring and comparison of Performance Indicators throughout the workflow of ongoing footbridge design projects. It also addresses the need for database scheme improvement and investigates data storage requirements. Despite existing flaws in the available database, the document highlights the applicability of the approach and proposes the introduction of a digital twin for future construction projects. It mentions the use of Sofistik software for structural engineering and carbon footprint calculation, with the computed values directly exported into the knowledge database. The primary actors involved in these activities are designers, civil engineers, and design companies, with data sourced from the Sbp (Schlaich bergemann partner) company database (partner of the ASHVIN project). The overall process for this feedback from past projects is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Process map for The Embodied Carbon Footprint Data use case

The use case was implemented for demonstration site #8 Footbridge in Germany.

3.6 #5 Quality Control of Installed Building Elements during Construction using Onsite Digital Twin Data

This document provides an in-depth overview and guidance on utilizing a Configuration Management based framework to enhance quality control in construction sites, with a focus on optimizing productivity, resource efficiency, safety, and reducing costs, all essential performance indicators of construction projects. The Configuration Management Use Case (CMT) has been deployed on multiple demonstration projects across Europe to ensure quality control of installed building elements during construction, utilizing onsite Digital Twin (DT) data. The successful implementation of this use case has resulted in significant improvements in resource efficiency, productivity, safety, and cost reduction at the construction sites under study. By employing Digital Twins as real-time feedback systems, the document explores the potential to link configuration information (CI) of installed products to the digital replica of the physical asset, enabling a more accurate representation of the asset throughout its lifecycle. This approach aims to minimize the number of changes required before commissioning the asset. The document outlines the process of construction site progress control, particularly in quality inspection and deviation checks, achieved by comparing the as-planned BIM model with the as-built digital twin data model obtained through laser scanners, RFID, BLE Beacon, and digital forms.

The process map given in Figure 10 gives an overview of directions for utilizing configuration management-based framework for quality assurance and management of building components installed at construction sites. It also assists in assessing the cost incurred based on the deviations from the configuration of building elements as defined in the design stage.

Figure 10 Process map for Quality Control of Installed Building Elements during Construction using Onsite Digital Twin Data use case.

The use case was implemented for demonstration site # 5 Kineum office building in Sweden.

3.7 #6 Digital Twinning of Concrete Consolidation Quality Process

The proposed use case aims to streamline the real-time monitoring of concrete consolidation quality by leveraging digital twin data obtained from construction sites. Accelerometers are utilized to measure formwork accelerations during concrete vibration, enabling continuous monitoring. This approach empowers the quality control team to achieve real-time quality assurance and promptly address issues related to concrete placement and vibration workmanship, particularly in scenarios where casting occurs continuously. Contrastingly, the current monitoring practice relies on subjective visual inspections and time-consuming feedback from project managers. As a result, poor workmanship may go undetected until concrete hardens, leading to retroactive quality control measures. Implementing a monitoring and warning solution for concrete placement and vibration workmanship quality is essential, particularly for continuous casting sites, to ensure real-time quality assurance and timely intervention. The overall process is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Process map for Digital Twinning of Concrete Consolidation Quality Process use case

The use case was implemented for demonstration site #6 Office building in Spain.

3.8 #7 GIS Integrator for Digital Twin Based Asset Management

A GIS application proposed in this use case enables asset managers to monitor the anticipated state of various assets based on their digital twins using a set of asset management key performance indicators. Utilizing a visualization, maintenance schedules may be designed with a thorough understanding of an asset's status, the corresponding output can be used to develop a risk model which considers different maintenance strategies and allows end-users to interactively review and utilize specific outputs of the risk assessment and the consequence modelling in the risk analysis.

The overall process map for the current use case based on GIS application is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Process Map

The use case was implemented for demonstration project #3 Zadar Airport Runway in Croatia.

3.9 #8 Risk-Based Status Assessment Use Case With Key Performance Indicators Dashboard

The proposed use case aims to present the asset managers with different maintenance scenarios based on the monitoring and condition assessment of the asset mainly utilizing image monitoring data from the site, taking into account the asset management defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), including safety, costs, productivity and environmental cost, to find the optimal maintenance scenarios to be performed within the determined time.

The use case also aims to aid the asset managers in understanding, how the data associated with assets can be acquired, populated, and employed to make decisions to increase efficiency, productivity, safety, and reduced cost of construction projects.

The overall process map for the use case based on the risk-based status assessment for generating maintenance scenarios is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 Process Map

The use case was implemented for demonstration project #3 Zadar Airport Runway in Croatia.

4 POPULATION OF THE PLATFORM ON ADDITIONAL CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS

4.1 Introduction

In its final year, the focus of the ASHVIN project was to expand the accessibility of its platform to more construction and maintenance projects. This involves collecting data from a variety of sources using IoT and image technologies, and integrating this data into the ASHVIN Digital Twin platform. From the project's outset, the goal has been to disseminate its innovative research findings to a wide range of stakeholders. This initiative aims to extend the benefits of ASHVIN's research to numerous building sites and infrastructure assets throughout Europe, extending beyond the initial 10 demonstration sites that have been instrumental in developing and testing the system. List of the additional construction project is shown in Table 12.

Table 12 Additional construction projects on which ASHVIN platform was populated.

no	Project	Country	Related phase of the process	Sensor system/data	Impact
1	Construction site of Züblin	Germany	Construction	3D laser scan	Productivity
2	Residential building	Poland	Construction	Camera on construction site, sensor on crane	Safety on site, Productivity
3	Wind tunnel building	Poland	Construction	Camera on construction site, sensor on crane	Safety on site, Productivity
4	National heritage bridge	Spain	Maintenance	Non-destructive techniques" ultrasound, mortar and bricks analysis	Safety on site
5	Zagreb airport	Croatia	Maintenance	Drone	Safety on site
6	Pula airport	Croatia	Maintenance	Drone	Safety on site
7	Bridge	Croatia	Maintenance	Drone	Safety on site
8	Single family house	Romania	Construction	Cameras	Productivity
9	Residential building	Romania	Construction	Cameras	Productivity
10	Office building	Sweden	Construction	Camera on construction site, sensor on crane	Productivity
11	Kindergarten	Poland	Maintenance	3D scan	More efficient design process
12	Office building in Gothenburg	Sweden	Maintenance	NavVis VLX 3 laser scanning	Improve design &

					monitoring process
13	Office building in Stockholm (1)	Sweden	Maintenance	NavVis VLX 3 laser scanning	Improve design& monitoring process
14	Office building in Stockholm (2)	Sweden	Maintenance	NavVis VLX 3 laser scanning	Improve design& monitoring process
15	Office building in Upsala	Sweden	Mainatance	NavVis VLX 3 laser scanning	Improve design& monitoring process
16	Single family house	Germany	Construction	Movement sensor (crane and saw)	Productivity
17	Urban excavation in Berlin	Germany	Construction	Displacement and Force Measurement	Safety on site
18	Urban excavation in Taiwan	Taiwan	Construction	Displacement and Force Measurement	Safety on site

The following chapters provide short overview of the selected additional construction projects, used sensing technology, describe data and processing and provide short recap of the expected benefits from using ASHVIN solutions.

4.1.1 Construction site of Züblin in Germany

4.1.1.1 Short summary

This additional construction site of Züblin is located in Nort-East of Germany. Regular laser scans of indoor finishing for a building were compared with as-built BIM models to track ongoing construction progress. The implementation allowed for better scheduling forecasting and for reduction of construction costs by better quality monitoring capabilities.

4.1.1.2 Description of sensing technology

Laser scans were conducted of approximate 5000 m2 indoor space using the NavVis LVX 3 laser scan system.

4.1.1.3 Description of data and processing

Data was processed using commercial scan to BIM software and imported in a dashboard to allow for tracking construction progress of installation of dry walls, dropped ceilings, and screed floors. For these objects the completed surfaces were automatically extracted. Percent completion values were reported in a web-based interface.

Figure 14 Laser scan and BIM model for construction site of Züblin in Germany

4.1.1.4 Expected benefits

Integration of laser scanning technology and BIM at Züblin's construction site has not only improved productivity by enabling better construction progress tracking and quality monitoring but has also contributed to resource efficiency and cost reduction through enhanced quality control and efficient data processing. By detecting and rectifying errors early, such as deviations in construction from the original plans, unnecessary rework and material wastage are minimized. Additionally, the ability to accurately track progress allows for more efficient resource allocation and scheduling, optimizing labour and material usage. As a result, construction costs are reduced while maintaining or even enhancing project quality.

4.1.2 Construction of residential buildings and wind tunnel in Poland

4.1.2.1 Short summary

The two additional construction sites are located in Gdansk, Poland. The first site is the construction of an ensemble of five residential buildings consisting of reinforced concrete. The second site is the construction of a wind tunnel, which also consisted of reinforced concrete.

Figure 15 ASHVIN team working on additional construction project in Gdańsk, Poland.

Fresh concrete was delivered by trucks, and the work process pattern executed by the tower crane consisted of the consecutive actions: Lifting down, Filling, Lifting up, Pouring concrete, Figure 16.

Figure 16 Operational flow of the work process pattern

4.1.2.2 Description of sensing technology

For each construction site we aimed to track crane movements. The cranes performed everyday work and concrete pouring for a certain duration. Therefore, we mounted the kinematic sensor system, which we had already used in previous demo sites, on the crane hook. The sensor, WTGAHRS2, consisted of an inertial measurement unit (IMU), a GPS tracker, and a barometer to collect three-axis (X/Y/Z) acceleration, three-axis angular velocity, three-axis angles,

longitude/latitude/altitude based on GPS, and altitude based on air pressure with a frequency rate of 4Hz. The sensor was connected to an ESP 32, which was connected to the internet via a mobile Wi-Fi router as construction-wide internet was unavailable. Due to the mobile internet connection, the ESP32 transferred the data in real-time to the IoT platform developed by Mainflux. A power bank supplied the whole sensor system with power.

Figure 17 Sensor system mounting on the crane hook for the residential buildings

Figure 18 shows sensor system mounting on the crane hook for the residential buildings

Figure 18 Sensor system mounting on the crane hook for the wind tunnel building

4.1.2.3 Description of data and processing

The sensor system mounted on the crane hook on the residential building demo site was mounted on the morning of one working day and disassembled the next day after work was finished. The sensor system collected data for 34 hours, 2 minutes, and 6 seconds, including non-working time during the night. Thus, the sensor system collected 502,346 data points with 13 data types. For the flight spot demo site, the sensor system collected the 13 data types for 5 hours, 36 minutes, and 5 seconds. The collected data are under analysis to extract activity durations similar to the analysis described in deliverable 3.3. Following data collection, we used a recurrent

neural network algorithm for classification. To investigate the performance, we calculated different performance metrics such as accuracy and the confusion matrix. We used the predicted instance by the classifier to calculate the action durations for each action repetition.

4.1.2.4 Expected benefits

The resulting data-based activity durations represent meaningful, up-to-date information and are further processed to determine the most suitable probability density functions (PDFs) for each action. We use the most suitable PDFs as input parameters for the DES tool to facilitate the management of upcoming work as described in deliverable 4.2. Deliverable 4.2 also depicts the formalism of the work process pattern. The DES tool calculates six KPIs (durations, productivity of workers and cranes, utilization of cranes, costs, and safety) and thus offers a beneficial evaluation of possible management decisions. The DES tool especially supports short-term management of construction processes by modelling and simulating different construction options, varying by resource allocations and delivery scenarios. Due to the usage of the DES tool, the impacts of different construction options can be compared, including best- and worst-case scenarios based on digital twin data. These simulation-based forecasts, considering real-time data, lead to a more productive, resource-efficient, and safer way of building.

The data acquired from the cameras installed on the construction site has been utilized to enhance health and safety procedures. An analysis has been conducted to automatically detect instances of health and safety equipment removal, such as construction helmets and vests. The objective is to enable automatic notifications to be sent to the construction site management when a worker, whether blue or white-collar, removes any part of their protective clothing.

4.1.3 National bridge in Spain

4.1.3.1 Short summary

Masonry arch bridges, scattered throughout numerous European cities and landscapes, are celebrated for their breath-taking and majestic designs. Built primarily from stone and/or brick, these structures have demonstrated remarkable durability and structural strength. They embody significant historical, scientific, and cultural importance, with many recognized as world heritage sites. The enduring nature of these bridges has played a crucial role in their sustained use and survival through hundreds of years. Nonetheless, these masonry constructions remain prone to various levels of permanent damage from natural disasters or ongoing exposure to environmental or usage-related wear, with their materials especially susceptible to such damages. Therefore, it's imperative to predict and prevent potential failures of these valuable structures. Adopting comprehensive monitoring strategies is essential in this process.

Figure 19 Additional bridge in Spain

4.1.3.2 Description of sensing technology

For material characterization, an overall inspection of a masonry arch bridge traditionally encompasses different techniques. Non-destructive testing (NDT) and minor destructive testing (MDT) techniques, or a combination of both allow assessing the state of the components of the structure at a given episode. Material characterization provides valuable insight related to the masonry components, i.e., mortars and units (fired clay or concrete bricks, cast or natural stones) and thus masonry as a homogenised continuum. In addition, static and dynamic proof load tests can shed light on the structural behaviour at structural levels while geometrical surveys and visual identification of singularities contribute to the overall understanding of the behaviour of the bridge. In addition, laser scanners provide a realistic depiction of the structure for geometrical purposes. Ashvin has contributed to the geometrical reproduction of the asset using laser scanners and photogrammetry.

Figure 20 Laser Scanning. Joncadella Bridge. Unprocessed point cloud

Figure 21 Laser Scanning. Joncadella Bridge. Unprocessed point cloud

4.1.3.3 Description of data and processing

The sensing procedure for assessing the condition of the bridge incorporates a comprehensive approach, beginning with the collection of Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) and Minor Destructive Testing (MDT) data to accurately characterise the materials involved. This is complemented by the acquisition of drone footage aimed at the geometric characterization of the structure. However, the bridge's location, surrounded by dense foliage, poses a challenge to obtaining clear drone footage, necessitating a careful evaluation of imagery quality and resolution. This limitation prompts the decision to employ laser scanners as an alternative method for precise data collection. Scheduled for deployment in March 2024, these laser scanners will enable the collection of detailed measurements essential for creating accurate models of the bridge. Utilising both the geometrical data from the drone and laser scanners, alongside the material characterization from NDT and MDT, enables the development of detailed models. These models are instrumental in assessing the current condition of the bridge, providing a thorough understanding of its structural integrity and informing necessary maintenance or conservation strategies.

4.1.3.4 Expected benefits

The primary goal of this project is to proactively predict potential collapses across various bridge types. To achieve this, the methodology centres on creating an extensive information system that integrates diverse data sources, including measurements and numerical models. This system will not only assimilate various data inputs but also incorporate analytical and predictive tools. Central to this approach is the geometric model, which is grounded in Heritage Building Information Modelling (HBIM) concepts. By combining H-BIM (Heritage BIM) with advanced data integration and analysis capabilities, the project aims to enhance bridge safety through early detection and prevention of structural failures. Figure 5 shows an overview of the encompassing techniques.

Figure 22 Different sources of information that must be encompassed together

4.1.4 Airports in Croatia

4.1.4.1 Short summary

Three additional airports have been inspected in Croatia, using drone, equipped with different sensors, namely high resolution camera, LiDAR sensor and thermal camera. Airports are one of the vital transport infrastructure, with a number of complex operations. One of the main objectives for the airport manager is to keep the runway safe and open. The airport maintenance process consists of different procedures and inspections to achieve an adequate level of safety for aircraft operations. These inspections include operational surfaces on the airport airside, and the process is performed manually with traditional technologies (with vehicles). The new approach is to use automated technologies in order to improve efficiency and reduce operational costs and greenhouse gas emissions. An unmanned aerial vehicle represents a potential alternative technology to replace traditional processes. Runways are particularly exposed to considerable loading and require daily inspections and monitoring because of high safety standards. The inspector should look for objects, contaminants, anomalies on the runway surface, that may endanger the safe landings and take-offs of aircraft such as: i) foreign object debris (FOD); ii) contaminants on the runway surface such as water, snow, spilled oil or fuel, or rubber deposit etc.; iii) cracks and potholes on the runway surface; iv) birds and wildlife on or in the vicinity of the runway. Instead of using vehicles for all operations, the intention is to replace some of them with UAVs. Such an approach may bring significant benefits: i) reduction of air pollution (in line with European Green Deal policy); ii) better efficiency of infrastructure inspection and higher accuracy of detection of anomalies on operational surfaces; iii) multiple measurements (inspection) per one drone operation; and iv) improvement of the Safety Management System at the airport.

Three additional case studies included: Zagreb airport, Pula airport and Mali Lošinj airport, which represent different size and exposure conditions.

Figure 23 and Figure 24 show location of three additional airports inspected in Croatia.

Figure 23 Additional airport in Croatia

Figure 24 On the left Mali Lošinj Airport and on the right Pula Airport

4.1.4.2 Description of sensing technology

For the inspection and monitoring of runway condition the unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) was used, equipped with a high resolution camera, thermal camera and LiDAR scanner. The aim was to replicate and validate the methodology developed

for Demo#3 Zadar airport. The implementation of remote sensing technologies can significantly improve and automate inspection and monitoring processes, enabling detection of foreign objects or defects at the very early stage (which often can be missed by a human eye), and continuous monitoring of any on-going deterioration process or damages. The time needed for an inspection is going to be decreased while increasing the inspections' quality. The collected data is used for a development of BIM or digital twin models, which enable continuous and accurate monitoring of the whole infrastructure, finally being used for the GIS-based asset management models and optimization of maintenance planning.

Figure 25 Usage of UAV for runway inspection

4.1.4.3 Description of data and processing

Detailed description of the data collection and processing are given in D3.1 and D5.4. High resolution images are used for the development of digital twin model and for damage detection. The final goal is to integrate the automated damage detection into inspection and maintenance planning process, as part of the asset management procedures. The primary goal of the approach embedded into GIS tool is to identify various surface flaws using visual data that was gathered through an UAV (Unmanned aerial vehicle) scanning of the runway area.

The aim of this additional sites was to replicate methodology and validate the operational procedure for the implementation of UAV for the visual inspection of runways, which would replace quarterly visual inspection. Digital recording of the damages over time, would not only increase the accuracy and repeatability of the inspection procedures, but it would also enable a development of performance prediction model.

Examples of images collected and processed data are shown on figures below.

Figure 26 Zagreb airport orthophoto map produced from high resolution images captured by drone (left) and LiDAR scan (right)

Figure 27 Airport Pula drone flight image (left) and different visualization of the captured runway surface presenting wet/dry conditions of the runway (right)

Figure 28 Pre-processing of images collected by UAV and implementing into GIS

4.1.4.4 Expected benefits

Expected benefits besides the digitalization and implementation of KPIs in the digital twin model, as described already in Demonstration project #3, are potentially also in the implementation of drone for daily inspections of runways and operational areas at airports. In the table below are impacts summarized for the size of the airport with around 3 km long runway. The impacts are related to the reduction of costs for vehicles and personnel, reduction of usage of resources (materials and energy) which reduces the environmental impacts, as shown in Table 13.

Table 13 Impacts for additional construction projects: Airports in Croatia.

Type of activity	Current annual costs	Benefits of UAV implementation		
		Direct costs	Environmental impacts	Personnel costs
Inspection of the pavement surfaces	117.000 km	Cost of the UAVs comparing to the costs of	UAV will fly ca 18-22 minutes per flight	The implementation of one piloted UAV

Regular control of the green areas near operating surface	3 Diesel Vehicles (purchase and maintenance costs) 24 tonnes of CO2 8.000 EUR costs of fuel Personnel costs 24 PM	the inspection cars is about 10 to 20 times lower	No usage of diesel = no CO2 pollution The increased knowledge of bird movements will decrease the risk of a wildlife disturbance. The usage of guns or any other destructive methods will be diminished.	which can collect data for different types of inspection Automatized post-processing models will decrease the time of detection for at least 50% and increase the accuracy of anomaly detection for at least 30% Personnel costs will decrease to approximately 10 PM
Inspections of the runway horizontal signage		No fuel costs		
Inspection of markings on taxiways				
Inspection of markings on aprons				
Inspection of signage				
Inspection of the lighting system of the operating area				
Inspection of obstacles limitation surfaces				
Wildlife inspection of the operating area				
5-year maintenance planning	Reactive and mostly post-damage decision making	Using DST will enable proactive decision making Minimum 30% lower maintenance costs	Usage of environmentally friendly materials will enable lower environmental impacts	Less need for subcontracting Better insights for the owner in the actual condition of the whole infrastructure
25-year investment planning	High risk decisions	Using DST different maintenance strategies /scenarios can be implemented and decisions can be made with less risk	Usage of environmentally friendly materials will enable lower environmental impacts (including climate change adaptation)	Optimization over the longer period of time

4.1.5 Bridge in Croatia

4.1.5.1 Short summary

Karlovac Bridge was inspected by bridge experts and by remotely operated drone with the aim to develop BIM model and detect condition assessment KPIs which will be implemented in the asset management system of the City of Karlovac. The bridge is located in the area of the City of Karlovac and overpasses the Kupa River on the DC1 state road (GP Macelj – Split), see Figure 29. The bridge structure consists of reinforced concrete structure over three spans (26m + 72m + 26m), in total 124 m long, together with embankments and abutment wings. The superstructure is based on Gerber girders, with two Gerber joints in the middle span. The span structure consists of 6 prefabricated reinforced concrete (RC) main girders in cross section at an axial distance of 335.0 cm, which are 175.0 cm high in the middle of the span and 250 cm above the piers. Main girders are 35.0 cm thick, with an extension to 55.0 cm in the lower part. They are connected by reinforced concrete transverse supports at intervals of approx. 800.0-900.0 cm. On the main girders there is an RC slab with cantilever overhangs of 220.0 cm on both sides of the bridge. Gerber span assemblies joints towards the abutments are additionally stiffened so that the main supports are at the bottom connected by RC plate.

The total width of the bridge with cornices is 22.15 m. The traffic area of the bridge consists of two lanes with a traffic in opposite directions, which are separated by a dividing strip on which on both sides there are derived elastic fences.

Figure 29 Karlovac bridge

Figure 30 Side view of the Karlovac bridge

Bridge was built in the early 1970's, and represents a typical reinforced concrete structure approximately 50 years old, with a number of deterioration and aging problems.

4.1.5.2 Description of sensing technology

Bridge was inspected by drone with a high resolution camera. The methodology for automated inspection and damage detection was developed within WP3 and WP5. The drone inspection was performed with the aim to detect following damages:

- Cracks (longitudinal and transversal) in the asphalt pavement
- Loss of asphalt layer
- Damages in the concrete elements (cracks, de-laminations, spalling)
- Exposed corroded reinforcement
- Stains of leakage and corrosion products
- Guardrail corrosion
- Transverse crack damage in asphalt expansion joint
- Vegetation growth on concrete surface

Images were processed afterwards with the aim to determine KPIs, related to condition and safety.

Figure 31 On the left drone image and on the right Point cloud model of the bridge

Figure 32 Development of BIM model and damage localization

4.1.5.3 Description of data and processing

Condition assessment of each bridge element is performed based on the detected individual damages. The detection of damages can be performed by manual visual inspection or with a drone equipped with a camera. In case a drone is used the whole process can be automated by using a damage detection model on captured images, as described in D3.1.

Condition assessment of structural elements was performed according to categorization in Table 2. Elements recognized in this condition assessment are superstructure concrete elements (bridge deck, girders) and the substructure concrete elements (columns and abutment). The result of the condition assessment is damage category for each element (e.g. bridge deck or main girders span 1 or column 1) which can then be summed up for overall bridge rating. Each damage category is associated with a colour coding, see Table 14. In the BIM model each element is coloured depending on its damage category allowing visualization of the current condition of the bridge elements.

Table 14 Categorization of defects for reinforced concrete elements

Damage category	Type of damage	Main performance indicators
0	No damage.	
I	Smaller defects resulted from the construction process.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Surface imperfections - Small cracks (shrinkage cracks)
II	Smaller defects resulted from the exploitation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Surface cracks - Delamination of surface cement paste film - Leaching of Ca(OH)₂
III	Defects that in long term decrease durability of the structure. Repair is needed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Network of cracks in concrete cover - Contamination of concrete cover (chloride, pH) - Concrete loss due to frost and de-icing salts damage
IV	Defects that can, in the foreseeable future, decrease the reliability of the structure. Repair is needed now.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Delamination, spalling of concrete cover (partially) - Honeycombs in concrete - Corrosion of steel visible - Loss of steel cross section due to corrosion
V	Defects that present a serious danger for safety of the structure. Intervention is needed emergently, and if necessary limitation or shutdown of traffic.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Delamination and spalling of concrete cover (full) - Advanced corrosion of steel, - Significant loss of steel cross section

4.1.5.4 Expected benefits

Performance indicators and Key performance indicators are provided in accordance with D5.1. The indicators are evaluated and implemented in the GISI model, in this case BIM model. Based on the Performance Indicators and KPIs for the safety, different maintenance scenarios can be developed using RISA model. Two approaches can be shown to evaluate the life time costs, reliability, availability and safety of considered bridge in the following 50 years.

Figure 33 Main components of the RISA tool

The implementation of RISA model (see Figure 33) includes following:

1. Obtain the probability of failure for the predefined failure mode of the particular asset under study based on monitoring and condition assessment form GIS.
2. Calculate the maintenance cost through time based on the predefined scenarios.
3. Estimate the user delays costs through time based on the predefined scenarios.
4. Estimate environmental costs through time based on the predefined scenarios.
5. Calculate risk through time based on the predefined scenarios.

Pre-conditions for the usage of the RISA tool is that the conditions of the asset under consideration should be monitored and assessed based on the user's requirements. Probability of failure should be calculated before using the RISA tool. When these preconditions are met then the tool can be used for development of well-assessed and condition-based maintenance scenarios for predictive maintenance. The RISA tool is aimed to be used throughout the whole life cycle of the asset, especially during its O&M cycle.

4.1.6 Construction of single family house in Romania

4.1.6.1 Short summary

This additional construction site of a single family house building is located in Iasi, Romania, Figure 34. Traditionally in Romania, the construction of such buildings is done by small companies, usually with rented equipment paid by the owner and managed and organized by the construction crew. The construction started on September 2023, and it is expected to end in September 2024.

Figure 34 Additional construction project: single family house in Iasi, Romania.

4.1.6.2 Description of sensing technology

The construction site is equipped with two cameras positioned for cross field recording. Each camera works as an independent unit, equipped with a small solar panel, batteries charged during the day by the solar panel, and 4G module that allow for cloud connectivity.

4.1.6.3 Description of data and processing

The data of this construction site consists of BIM model that is updated regularly to reflect the as-built situation on the construction site. The data from the two camera consist of small recordings consisting in video snapshots with the length of 30 seconds.

4.1.6.4 Expected benefits

The expected benefits from the current implementation are progress monitoring, resources usage, quality control and assurance, and safety.

4.1.7 Construction of residential building in Romania

4.1.7.1 Short summary

This additional construction site is located in Iasi, Romania, Figure 35. The construction is expected to start in the summer of the 2024. The existing building will be subjected to partial demolition and retrofitting, to support the additional two floors extension. For this site, **digitAEC** is the consultant of the owner of the building, advising and helping the client to implement a digital twin for both, construction and operation of the asset.

Figure 35 Additional construction project: residential building in Iasi, Romania.

4.1.7.2 Description of sensing technology

The foreseen sensing technologies, that are currently tested are consisting of:

- environment sensors for indoor air quality - the collects temperature, humidity, air particles load, CO2, noise intensity, and vibrations,
- Time-lapse cameras that will be installed inside,
- drone for video recording that will be flown outside.

4.1.7.3 Description of data and processing

The data of this project consists of BIM Models of the existing and proposed situation, environmental data collected by indoor sensors, time-lapse recordings for the indoors construction activities, and outside video recordings for the outdoor construction activities. It is foreseen that the data from the time-lapse cameras as well as from the drone, will first go through a processing filter using edge devices to ensure privacy, before being sent to the storage device/server. Later, collected data will be processed using machine learning algorithms to support the use cases listed on the next section for the expected benefits.

4.1.7.4 Expected benefits

The expected benefits of the data planned to be collected construction progress monitoring, health and safety during construction and operation, quality assurance and control.

4.1.8 Construction of office building in Sweden (Habitat 7)

4.1.8.1 Short summary

The 8,000 m² and nine floor office building Habitat 7 is located in central Göteborg, Sweden. The construction of the building, which is being carried out using solid wood technology, involves a hybrid frame of climate-smart concrete and wood. This design aims to minimize environmental impact and is set to receive BREEAM Excellent level sustainability certifications. These certifications take into account various factors such as the building's energy efficiency, indoor comfort, water use, and waste management.

In this project, NCC, the construction company, has prioritized the frame, foundation, and facade. These components account for approximately 70 percent of the carbon dioxide load in a typical office building.

Particular attention had to be paid to the foundation piling due to the fact that Habitat 7, the building in question, would be built on clay with a high groundwater level. To address this, NCC replaced steel piles with wooden ones at the bottom, where the clay is low in oxygen and wood doesn't deteriorate, while concrete was used at the top.

The completion of Habitat 7 is scheduled for the first quarter of 2025. This project exemplifies a thoughtful approach to sustainable construction, balancing environmental considerations with practical constraints.

4.1.8.2 Description of sensing technology

The intermediate floors consist of wood, and concrete will be poured onto these to meet acoustic requirements. Since no weather protection is employed in the project, 50 sensors have been strategically placed inside the exterior walls and on the

building's floors. These sensors measure temperature and relative humidity in the air, transmitting the data wirelessly to a database accessible through a web-based interface. By integrating the sensors into the exterior walls, early water leaks can be detected without the need for visual inspection, eliminating the necessity for structural dismantling. If a moisture leak occurs, the sensors can indicate an elevated moisture level before the production staff can visually identify the issue. The sensors have an operating lifespan of several years and will remain in place once the building is completed. Consequently, even during the building's operational phase, they can detect moisture leaks, even after the production organization has handed over the building to the client and the tenants have moved into the building.

Additionally, sensors are positioned inside the building to measure moisture levels and minimize damage to the wooden frame caused by moisture. Later, during concrete casting, the sensors will regulate indoor temperature and relative humidity in the air, ensuring effective concrete drying.

Furthermore, we collected kinematic data by mounting the WTGAHRS2-based sensor system, which was described above in detail, on the hook of a tower crane and on the hook of a mobile crane to track operations. The sensor mounted on the crane hook collected data with a frequency rate of 4HZ and the mobile crane with a frequency rate of 2Hz.

Figure 36 Construction of office building in Sweden (Habitat 7)

The two cranes were used to mount prefabricated wood components at the building following the work process pattern in Deliverable 4.2. Figure 37 presents the operational flow of the work process pattern.

Figure 37 Operational flow of the work process pattern

4.1.8.3 Description of data and processing

The database collects data that includes indoor temperature, relative humidity, and absolute humidity, both indoors and in the exterior wall structures, as well as outdoor temperature and outdoor humidity levels. This approach allows us to calculate the moisture addition to the building, which depends on the daily operations at the construction site. Given that the frame is made of wood, we aim for an indoor climate that maintains a moisture level that prevents rapid drying of the frame while avoiding exceeding critical moisture levels that could lead to damage. Leveraging the database, both the construction site personnel and the remote moisture specialist can monitor the indoor climate and adjust the indoor temperature as needed. For instance, during cold and dry indoor conditions, we lower the indoor temperature to mitigate moisture loss. Conversely, when the outdoor climate is warmer and more humid, we raise the indoor temperature to ensure that the warm air can handle a higher moisture load.

Kinematic data

Regarding the tower crane, we collected data for around 25 hours and 58 minutes resulting in a data set of 448,720 data points. For the mobile crane we collected data for 27 hours and 5 minutes resulting in a data set consisting of 187,225 data points. Both dataset include non-working time during the night. Due to adverse weather conditions during data collection, construction was not executed continuously on site as the crane operations would be too risky due to heavy wind and rain. The data collection could be observed in real-time on mobile phones or computers.

In the data analysis for both data sets, we first labelled the data by comparing the collected data with a recorded video from the site. Next, we calculated sliding windows with 50% and the features min, max, mean, interquartile range, and root mean square error. The resulting sliding windows were used for 5-fold cross validation for the tower crane data and for 10-fold cross validation for the mobile crane using XGBosst classifier. To investigate the predictions, we calculated performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1. Finally, we processed the predicted instances of the classifier to calculate action durations for each repetition.

4.1.8.4 Expected benefits

Moisture Management: By monitoring indoor and outdoor humidity levels, the system ensures that the wooden frame of the building maintains an optimal moisture level. This prevents rapid drying, which could lead to structural issues, while avoiding excessive moisture that might cause damage.

Early Leak Detection: The integration of sensors into exterior walls allows for early detection of water leaks. This proactive approach helps identify leaks before they become visible, eliminating the need for costly and time-consuming ocular inspections or structural dismantling.

Continuous Monitoring: The database enables real-time monitoring of the indoor climate. Construction site personnel and remote moisture specialists can access data remotely, allowing them to make informed decisions and adjust indoor temperature settings as needed.

Concrete Drying Control: During concrete casting, the sensors play a crucial role in regulating indoor temperature and relative humidity. This helps secure effective concrete drying, contributing to the overall quality of the construction.

Long-Term Operation: The sensors have a long operational lifespan and remain in place even after the building is completed. This ensures ongoing monitoring during the building's operational phase, even after it has been handed over to tenants.

The extracted durations from the kinematic data represent meaningful information for the DES tool. The data-based durations are further processed to determine the most suitable PDFs for each action. Next, we use the resulting PDFs as input parameters for the DES tool. In the DES tool, we have the possibility to test different options considering resource allocations and delivery scenarios. The tool models and simulates a multitude of possible options stochastically and calculates the six stated KPIs as described in deliverable 4.2: durations, productivity for workers and cranes, resource efficiency crane, costs, and safety. Thus, the impacts of different management decisions can be forecasted in consideration of expected, but also extreme scenarios, such as best- and worst-case scenarios. Overall, the DES tool usage based on real-time data improves performance in relation to the calculated KPIs, resulting in more productive, resource-efficient, and safer construction.

4.1.9 Office buildings in Sweden

4.1.9.1 Short summary

In total four office locations in Sweden, two in Stockholm, one in Uppsala and the final one in Gothenburg, underwent analysis. One of these office spaces was subjected to scanning in order to generate point clouds, which were then processed through scan-2-BIM procedure to generate BIM models, Figure 38. This was because the office location is considered a heritage building from the 17th century and therefore no up to date drawings were accessible. The other three were generated into 3D models from drawings.

Figure 38 Cloud point and BIM model of the offices in Sweden

Following this, sensors to monitor air quality, temperature, and noise levels were installed at the offices and geographically positioned within the generated scan-2-BIM models. This process enhances maintenance operations and can be used to improve environmental factors.

4.1.9.2 Description of sensing technology

The offices were scanned using NavVis VLX 3 laser scanning. This generated a detailed point cloud as well as 360° images of the entire office.

4.1.9.3 Description of data and processing

The point cloud scanning data was processed to generate scan-2-BIM models.

4.1.9.4 Expected benefits

The expected benefits of the office spaces are aimed at the maintenance stage. Measuring temperature, air quality and occupancy rate. The desired outcome is to improve the environmental factors in all office locations.

4.1.10 Urban excavations in Germany, Taiwan and the USA

4.1.10.1 Short summary

The approach adopted in *Data Driven Risk Management* was performed on publicly available data from three urban excavations in Germany, Taiwan and the USA. An approach was taken which incorporates geotechnical site investigation data into a numerical model of the excavation, following the same approach developed for Demonstration Case #10 in ASHVIN. The model is then validated based on the observed measurement data.

Figure 39 Numerical model of the excavation

To improve the updating efficiency and speed of future digital twin platforms, a machine learning-based “surrogate model” was trained on simulations run in the validated numerical model. This surrogate model essentially approximates the behaviour of the numerical model, understanding the dependencies between the inputs and a specific output, leading to a substantial improvement in computational time (from two minutes per simulation to less than a second) whilst maintaining a sufficient degree of accuracy.

Figure 40 Numerical model

4.1.10.2 Description of sensing technology

Measurements include wall and ground displacement as well as anchor/strut force.

4.1.10.3 Description of data and processing

Site investigation data, including Cone Penetration Testing and lab testing, were gathered for analysis. Monitoring data, encompassing measurements of wall displacement, ground settlement, and data from load cells and strain gauges, were continuously recorded throughout the project. A numerical model was constructed using the Finite Element Method, serving as the foundation for developing the dataset required for the surrogate model. Machine learning techniques, specifically artificial neural networks, were employed to implement predictive modelling and analysis within the project framework.

4.1.11 Expected benefits

Calibrated model parameter selection based on correlations enhances the reliability of assessing excavation stability during construction. Surrogate modelling facilitates improved computational time within digital twin platforms. Decreasing the time needed to run thousands of simulations enhances reliability and enables probabilistic-based analyses. The surrogate model presents potential avenues for updating model inputs based on observations, utilizing methods such as the Observational Method and Bayesian updating. There is potential for future development of easily usable surrogate models to manage whole-life performance effectively.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The ASHVIN project, over its 3.5 years, has created the ASHVIN toolkit for design, construction, and maintenance phases. The toolkit was tested in demonstration cases, providing valuable insights for improvement. For a number of the developed ASHVIN tools, specific use cases were documented and are available publicly on the [Zenodo](#) platform. The use cases were developed based on the template provided by the BuildingSMART (www.buildingsmart.org) enabling the adoption of the ASHVIN developed tools for other external digital twin platforms to achieve wider adoption of digital twins throughout the lifecycle of the AEC industry, investors, building owners, and facility managers.

The ASHVIN platform has been proven to be able to support and integrate the developed ASHVIN toolkit. The ASHVIN platform enables a lifecycle data driven approach to the construction sector, where decision making can be made on objective data and information, which is something that the ASHVIN toolkit promotes. The ASHVIN platform further enables the seamless exchange of data with an IoT connectivity which can help transition the construction industry lifecycle from a largely fragmented industry to a more collaborative and standardised industry. Here the language exchange utilized across the project lifecycle and the ASHVIN toolkit can be standardised through the ASHVIN ontology and standardised processes.

The ASHVIN toolkit enables the evaluation of the ASHVIN Key Performance Indicators (Productivity, Resource Efficiency, Safe construction works, Cost) within the ASHVIN platform through both KPI dashboards and through visualisations. The 10 demonstration projects as well as the additional projects added during the last year of the ASHVIN contribute to various areas of the lifecycle focus phases of the project.

The variety of demonstration projects has allowed developing digital twins solutions with a very broad perspective. This is one of the main strengths of the project. The project's diverse demonstration projects have provided a comprehensive perspective, showing the importance of flexibility for different stakeholders and applications in digital twin solutions. In a given site, many applications may give/extract value to/from its corresponding digital twin.